

1 **Increased water-use efficiency translates into contrasting growth patterns of Scots pine**
2 **and sessile oak at their southern distribution limits**

3 **Running title:** Contrasting growth to water-use efficiency

4 Elisabet Martínez-Sancho^{1*}, Isabel Dorado-Liñán², Emilia Gutiérrez-Merino³, Michael Matiu¹,
5 Gerhard Helle⁴, Ingo Heinrich⁴ and Annette Menzel^{1,5}

6 ¹*Ecoclimatology, Department of Ecology and Ecosystem Management, Technische Universität*
7 *München, Hans-Carl-von-Carlowitz-Platz 2, 85354 Freising, Germany*

8 ²*Departamento de Silvicultura y Gestión de los Sistemas Forestales, CIFOR-INIA, Carretera*
9 *de la Coruña Km 7,5, 28040, Madrid, Spain*

10 ³*Departament of Biological Evolution, Ecology and Environmental Sciences, Universitat de*
11 *Barcelona, Av. Diagonal 643, 08028 Barcelona, Spain*

12 ⁴*Section 5.2 Climate Dynamics and Landscape Evolution, GFZ – German Research Centre for*
13 *Geosciences, Telegrafenberg, 14473 Potsdam, Germany*

14 ⁵*Institute for Advanced Study, Technische Universität München, Lichtenbergstraße 2a,*
15 *85748 Garching, Germany*

16

17 * Corresponding author:

18 Elisabet Martínez-Sancho
19 Technische Universität München, Ecoclimatology, Department of Ecology and Ecosystem
20 Management

21 Hans-Carl-von-Carlowitz 2, 85354, Freising, Germany

22 E-mail: martinez@wzw.tum.de

23 Phone: +49 8161-714740

24 Fax: +49 8161-714753

25

26

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30

31 **Abstract**

32 In forests, the increase of atmospheric CO₂ concentrations (*Ca*) has been related to enhanced
33 tree growth and intrinsic water-use efficiency (*iWUE*). However, in drought-prone areas such
34 as the Mediterranean Basin it is not yet clear to what extent this ‘fertilizing’ effect may
35 compensate for drought-induced growth reduction. We investigated tree growth and
36 physiological responses at five Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) and five sessile oak (*Quercus*
37 *petraea* (Matt.) Liebl.) sites located at their southernmost distribution limits in Europe for the
38 period 1960-2012 using annually resolved tree-ring width and $\delta^{13}C$ data to track
39 ecophysiological processes. Results indicated that all ten natural stands significantly increased
40 their leaf intercellular CO₂ concentration (*Ci*), and consequently *iWUE*. Different trends in the
41 theoretical gas exchange scenarios as a response to increasing *Ca* were found: generally, *Ci*
42 tended to increase proportionally to *Ca*, except for trees at the driest sites in which *Ci* remained
43 constant. *Ci* from the oak sites displaying higher water availability tended to increase at a
44 comparable rate to *Ca*. Multiple linear models fitted at site level to predict basal area increment
45 (*BAI*) using *iWUE* and climatic variables better explained tree growth in pines (31.9 - 71.4%)
46 than in oak stands (15.8 - 46.8%). *iWUE* was negatively linked to pine growth whereas its effect
47 on growth of oak differed across sites. Tree growth in the western and central oak stands was
48 negatively related to *iWUE*, whereas *BAI* from the easternmost stand was positively associated
49 with *iWUE*. Thus, some *Q. petraea* stands might have partially benefited from the ‘fertilizing’
50 effect of rising *Ca*, whereas *P. sylvestris* stands due to their strict closure of stomata did not
51 profit from increased *iWUE* and consequently showed in general growth reductions across sites.
52 Additionally, the inter-annual variability of *BAI* and *iWUE* displayed a geographical polarity in
53 the Mediterranean.

54

55 **Introduction**

56 The increase of CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere (*Ca*), especially since the second half of
57 the last century, has direct and indirect impacts on the functioning of forest ecosystems, on their
58 productivity and the distribution of species (Körner, 2000; Allen, 2009; Jones *et al.*, 2009; Zhao
59 & Running, 2010; Anderegg *et al.*, 2013). Among the global climatic effects, it is well known
60 that the increase of *Ca* is one of the main drivers of current global warming, which leads to an
61 increase of global mean temperature and in the course of the climate change also to changes in
62 precipitation patterns. Specifically, for southern Europe, the most severe scenario of the last
63 IPCC (2013) assessment report predicted an increase of ~7°C in summer temperature and a
64 decrease of ~30% in April-September precipitation, as well as a higher frequency of extreme
65 summer droughts by the end of the 21st century (Giorgi, 2006; Mariotti, 2010; Collins *et al.*,
66 2013). Higher temperatures may promote an extension of the growing season (Menzel &
67 Fabian, 1999; Menzel *et al.*, 2006; Gordo & Sanz, 2010). However, in areas such as the
68 Mediterranean region where water availability is already limited (Giorgi & Lionello, 2008) and
69 land-use changes are increasing the competition for this resource (Ruiz-Benito *et al.*, 2013),
70 these conditions will also likely result in higher water stress (Lindner *et al.*, 2010).

71 Additionally to the global climatic effects of *Ca* on forest ecosystems, *Ca* also directly affects
72 plant physiology by modifying carbon-water relationships within the plant (Körner, 2000). An
73 increase in *Ca* reduces stomatal conductance (*g_s*) (Field *et al.*, 1995) and at the same time,
74 stimulates higher photosynthetic rates (*A*) (Ainsworth & Rogers, 2007). It has been
75 demonstrated that photosynthesis in most of the C₃ plants will remain below saturation levels
76 even at twice-current *Ca* levels (Körner *et al.*, 2007), and consequently, plants might still benefit
77 from higher *Ca*. The reduction in *g_s*, the enhancement of *A* and/or the combination of both are
78 the primary causes of the worldwide increase of intrinsic water-use efficiency (*iWUE*: the
79 amount of carbon uptake per unit of water loss; Farquhar *et al.*, 1982) during the last century

80 (Saurer *et al.*, 2004, 2014; Peñuelas *et al.*, 2011; Frank *et al.*, 2015). Hence, a stimulation of
81 plant growth is expected due to this ‘CO₂-fertilization’ effect on *A* and the reduced water
82 consumption of plants (Morgan *et al.*, 2007; Wertin *et al.*, 2010). However, this ‘fertilization’
83 effect could be overridden by other limiting factors such as nutrients (Norby *et al.*, 2010), and
84 must counterbalance the negative drought effects induced by global climate change (Andreu-
85 Hayles *et al.*, 2011; Franks *et al.*, 2013). The net direct and indirect effects of these atmospheric
86 changes will largely affect growth, functioning and forest distribution in the Mediterranean
87 Basin (Keenan *et al.*, 2011).

88 Tree-ring records are a valuable source of information to infer long-term physiological and
89 growth changes over time (McCarroll & Loader, 2004). The isotopic discrimination against ¹³C
90 that occurs in the leaves (i.e., diffusion and carboxylation fractionations) is reflected in the
91 stable carbon isotope ratios and hence in the isotopic signature ($\delta^{13}C$) of the organic matter of
92 a specific year. Farquhar *et al.* (1982 and 1989) demonstrated that there is a linear relationship
93 between carbon isotopic discrimination and leaf physiology in such a way that $\delta^{13}C$ is directly
94 related to *A* and *g_s*, which is translated into *iWUE* as the ratio between the two processes. In
95 recent studies using annually resolved tree-ring $\delta^{13}C$, Frank *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that
96 *iWUE* of *Quercus* species across Europe increased by 14%, and of coniferous species by 22%
97 solely due to *Ca* increase. However, to what extent does this increase in *iWUE* account for
98 growth enhancement? Some studies globally assessing the relationship between growth and
99 *iWUE* generally found a lack or only small effects of *iWUE* on growth (Peñuelas *et al.*, 2011;
100 Silva & Anand, 2013; van der Sleen *et al.*, 2014 for the tropics). Consequently, more research
101 is needed that specifically considers the global climate effects, especially the interactions
102 between temperature and drought (Matiu *et al.* 2017), and physiological effects of increased *Ca*
103 which are not considered as being spatially uniform (Saurer *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, in the last
104 decades, plant physiologists have reported contrasting strategies among plant functional groups
105 (e.g. isohydric and anisohydric species) to cope with drought, although some recent studies

106 claim that this classification is rather continuous than categorical (Klein, 2014; Martínez-Vilalta
107 & Garcia-Forner, 2016; Matías *et al.*, 2016). Indeed, differences in water-use efficiency and
108 transpiration between and within functional plant groups at different scales in Europe (Frank *et*
109 *al.*, 2015) point to the need to zoom in from global studies to species-specific and regional
110 approaches to assess the long-term effects of rising *Ca*.

111 Special attention needs to be given to temperate and boreal tree species reaching their southern
112 distribution limits in the Mediterranean region (so called rear-edge populations according to
113 Hampe and Petit, 2005), such as *Quercus petraea* (Thuiller, 2003) and *Pinus sylvestris* (Galiano
114 *et al.*, 2010). In the Mediterranean region they already face suboptimal environmental
115 conditions compared to the center of their distribution areas. Warming and reduced water
116 availability have caused forest die-back episodes in the Mediterranean Basin (Allen *et al.*,
117 2010), and consequently shifts of most temperate tree species' ranges towards northern latitudes
118 are expected to occur in the 21st century.

119 Although some studies have analyzed the relationship between *iWUE* and growth of temperate
120 species at their rear-edges (Linares & Camarero, 2012; Granda *et al.*, 2014; Hereş *et al.*, 2014;
121 Lévesque *et al.*, 2014), they were mostly focused on one single location/ area. Thus, we intend
122 to study a larger number of stands of Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) and sessile oak (*Quercus*
123 *petraea* (Matt.) Liebl.) distributed along the southernmost limit of the species' ranges. We
124 expect to ascertain under which climatic conditions (in which localities) trees show signs of
125 vulnerability. Our specific objectives are (i) to test if rising atmospheric CO₂ concentrations
126 and changes in climate may have induced species-specific changes in tree growth and
127 ecophysiological parameters; (ii) to determine how and to what extent changes in climate and
128 in *iWUE* are related to radial growth rates; and (iii) to assess species-specific and/or site-specific
129 physiological adjustments to increased atmospheric CO₂ concentrations over the studied period.

130 **Materials and methods**

131 *Study species and sites*

132 Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.; pine, hereafter) is an evergreen temperate to boreal conifer tree
133 species that has the largest distribution range of all species of the genus *Pinus*. This broad
134 ecological range denotes a high degree of structural and functional plasticity. Pine is considered
135 a relatively isohydric species with a high sensitivity of stomatal conductance to vapour pressure
136 deficits (Irvine *et al.*, 1998; Leo *et al.*, 2014; Salmon *et al.*, 2015). In contrast, sessile oak
137 (*Quercus petraea* (Matt.) Liebl.; oak, hereafter) is a deciduous temperate tree species
138 predominantly distributed in central Europe. It has been described as a relatively anisohydric
139 species due to the capacity of maintaining relatively high transpiration and stomatal
140 conductance during drought periods in comparison to other temperate tree species (Bréda *et al.*,
141 1993; Epron & Dreyer, 1993; Aranda *et al.*, 2000; Klein, 2014), most likely due to a deep
142 rooting system (Bréda *et al.*, 1993).

143 Five natural stands of pine and five of oak were selected across the southernmost limit of both
144 species distributions (Figure 1). The study sites cover a wide longitudinal range across the
145 northern rim of the Mediterranean Basin (41.7° N – 45.8° N and 2.0° E – 24.0° E) (Table 1).
146 The western and central Mediterranean stands Sant Llorenç del Munt (LLO_{ES}, Spain), Can
147 Figueroles (CFI_{ES}, Spain), Cuébris (CUE_{FR}, France), Baiardo (BIO_{IT}, Italy), Roccheta
148 Tanaro/Asti (AST_{IT}, Italy), Monte Sole (MON_{IT}, Italy) and Dolenja (DOL_{SI}, Slovenia) are
149 located in the Mediterranean Mountains or Mediterranean North environmental zone (Metzger
150 *et al.*, 2005). These sites are characterized by a typical Mediterranean climate with a significant
151 drop in precipitation in summer and one or two maxima of precipitation during the colder
152 months. On the other hand, the eastern stands Sushitsa (SUS_{BG}, Bulgaria), Velingrad (VEL_{BG},
153 Bulgaria) and Focsani (FOS_{RO}, Romania) are in the Continental and Pannonian environmental
154 zone (Metzger *et al.*, 2005) with continuous and rather uniformly distributed rainfall over the
155 year, with a maximum precipitation in late spring and temperatures below zero during winter.

156 Mean annual temperatures and total annual precipitation obtained from the CRU TS3.23 dataset
157 (Harris *et al.*, 2014) for the study period (1960-2012) ranged from 7.2 to 13.9 C° and from 523
158 to 1674 mm, respectively (Table 2). Among the pine stands, BIO_{IT} was the warmest site and
159 VEL_{BG} is the coldest. For the oak stands, CFI_{ES} is the warmest, and DOL_{SI} and SUS_{BG} are the
160 coldest ones. Regarding precipitation, pines stands received a similar amount of annual
161 precipitation with LLO_{ES} and VEL_{BG} having slightly lower cumulative annual precipitation.
162 Precipitation differences among oak stands were higher than among pine stands. CFI_{ES}, SUS_{BG}
163 and FOS_{RO} displayed lower annual precipitation sums (694.0, 665.4 and 523.8 mm,
164 respectively) than AST_{IT} and DOL_{SI} (1042.0 and 1674.9 mm, respectively). The annual aridity
165 index (P/PET) was rather uniform across the pine sites ranging from 0.7 (LLO_{ES}) to 1.1
166 (MON_{IT}), whereas the oak sites showed a larger range (from 0.6 to 2.5) with the central oak
167 stands, AST_{IT} and DOL_{SI}, exhibiting higher values.

168 *Tree-ring width chronologies*

169 At each study site, two increment cores per tree were extracted at breast height from more than
170 twenty dominant or co-dominant trees. Additionally, diameter at breast height and total height
171 of the trees were measured (Table 1). The 5-mm cores were air dried and sanded with
172 progressively finer sanding paper until the rings were visible. Cores were visually cross-dated
173 under a binocular microscope (Stokes & Smiley, 1968; Fritts, 1976). Tree-ring widths were
174 measured to a precision of 0.01 mm using LINTAB measuring device (Rinntech, Heidelberg,
175 Germany). The correct dating and the quality of the measurements were checked with the
176 programme COFECHA (Holmes, 1983). For each tree, ring-width measurements of the two
177 cores were averaged. Afterwards, these series were converted to basal area increment (*BAI*, cm²
178 year⁻¹) in order to remove the age trend inherent in ring-width series. *BAI* was used as a
179 surrogate of secondary growth (Biondi & Quedan, 2008); and it was obtained as:

$$180 \quad BAI = \pi(r_t^2 - r_{t-1}^2) \quad (1),$$

181 where r is the tree radius and t is the year of tree-ring formation. The calculation of BAI was
182 performed using the R package `dplR` (Bunn, 2008).

183 *Isotope chronologies*

184 For isotope measurements, five representative and undamaged cores from five healthy trees
185 were selected per site. All sampled trees were older than 70 years in order to avoid the effect of
186 juvenile wood on the carbon isotope ratios (Leavitt, 2010). The holocellulose extraction
187 followed the procedures described by Schollaen *et al.* (2015) applying a novel cross-section
188 extraction method, which is a re-design of the technique proposed by Kagawa *et al.* (2015). The
189 main advantage of this technique is the time reduction invested in each sample since it allows
190 the cellulose extraction of different rings at the same time. We focused on holocellulose because
191 isotopic differences between holo- and α - cellulose were found to be very small and constant in
192 time (Boettger *et al.*, 2007; Wieloch *et al.*, 2011). The extraction of holocellulose employed
193 acetic acid, sodium chlorite and sodium hydroxide as described in Loader *et al.* (1997).

194 After cellulose extraction, the annual tree-ring cellulose sections were split using a scalpel: the
195 whole rings were considered for pine whereas only latewood was sampled for oak. Oak
196 earlywood was discarded because the carbon incorporated in this section mostly comes from
197 carbohydrate reserves established in the previous year (Helle & Schleser, 2004), whereas oak
198 latewood constitutes a mixture of new assimilates and reserves, similarly to pine wood.
199 Afterwards, all samples underwent homogenization using an ultrasonic device (Laumer *et al.*,
200 2009) and freeze drying. An accurate mass of each sample was loaded in a tin capsule.
201 Measurements of stable carbon isotopes were undertaken by combustion using an elemental
202 analyser (Model NA 1500; Carbo Erba, Milan, Italy) coupled online via open split to an
203 Isoprime IRMS (Isoprime Ltd, Cheadle Hulme, UK). The isotope ratios are given in the delta
204 (δ) notation, relative to the standard VPDB (Vienna-PDB).

205 The $\delta^{13}C$ raw data were used to calculate the carbon isotope discrimination against ^{13}C (Δ) and
206 it was defined as:

$$207 \quad \Delta = \frac{(\delta^{13}C_{air} - \delta^{13}C_{plant})}{(1 + \delta^{13}C_{plant}/1000)} \quad (2),$$

208 which corrects for the increasingly $\delta^{13}C$ depleted atmospheric CO₂ due to fossil fuel burning
209 since the beginning of industrialization (Tans *et al.*, 1979). For C3 plants, Δ is linearly related
210 to leaf gas exchange and plant physiology by the following equation (Farquhar *et al.*, 1982,
211 1989):

$$212 \quad \Delta = a + (b - a) \frac{C_i}{C_a} \quad (3)$$

213 where a is the constant associated with fractionation during CO₂ diffusion through the stomata
214 (4.4‰; O'Leary, 1981), b is the constant associated with fractionation during carboxylation
215 (27‰; Farquhar and Richards, 1984), and C_i and C_a are the intercellular and atmospheric
216 concentrations of CO₂ ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$), respectively. The values of C_a and $\delta^{13}C_{air}$ have increased
217 and decreased, respectively, over the last two centuries due to the combustion of isotopically
218 depleted fossil fuel. These values were obtained combining data from McCarroll and Loader,
219 (2004) and from Mauna Loa records (available at <http://cdiac.ornl.gov/>). The intrinsic water-
220 use efficiency ($iWUE$) is the ratio of the assimilation rate (A) and stomatal conductance of water
221 vapor (g_w):

$$222 \quad iWUE = \frac{A}{g_w} \cong \frac{g_{CO_2}(C_a - C_i)}{g_w} \cong \frac{1}{1.6} (C_a - C_i) \quad (4)$$

223 Time series of BAI , $\delta^{13}C$, Δ , C_i and $iWUE$ with annual resolution were established for the period
224 1960-2012.

225 *Theoretical gas-exchange scenarios*

226 The temporal trends of C_i/C_a , which is the relationship between carbon uptake and atmospheric
227 carbon, were calculated and compared to the three theoretical scenarios for the regulation of
228 plant-gas exchange fractionation during CO₂ diffusion through the stomata (see Saurer *et al.*,
229 2004). These scenarios differ in the degree in which C_i follows changes on C_a : (1) either not at
230 all ($C_i = \text{constant}$), (2) in a proportional way ($C_i/C_a = \text{constant}$) or (3) at the same rate ($C_a - C_i$
231 $= \text{constant}$). In scenario 1, C_i remains constant indicating a reduction of the C_i/C_a ratio, which
232 is most probably due to a strong stomatal closure. Scenario 2 reflects a proportional regulation
233 of C_i by photosynthesis and stomatal conductance, resulting in constant C_i/C_a . In scenario 3,
234 C_i follows exactly the increase in C_a , which represents a relatively weak stomatal response
235 increasing the C_i/C_a ratio.

236 *Statistical analyses*

237 CRU data were extracted from the closest point to each study site and contain monthly mean
238 temperature, monthly total precipitation and mean potential evapotranspiration (calculated
239 using the Penman–Monteith equation) gridded at a 0.5° spatial resolution. Annual mean
240 temperature and total precipitation, as well as the ratio between total annual precipitation and
241 the potential annual evapotranspiration (P/PET) were calculated for all study sites. Total
242 seasonal precipitation, mean seasonal temperature and mean seasonal aridity index (P/PET)
243 were also calculated for winter (previous December, January and February), spring (March,
244 April and May), summer (June, July and August) and autumn (September, October and
245 November).

246 Linear trends during the study period (1960-2012) were calculated using least-squares
247 regressions for annual and seasonal climatic variables (temperature, precipitation and P/PET)
248 as well as BAI , $\delta^{13}C$, Δ , C_i and $iWUE$. The similarities of the relation between C_i and C_a trends
249 obtained from the $\delta^{13}C$ -values and the three theoretical gas exchange scenarios were quantified
250 by root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) per study site. Furthermore,

251 we related C_i/C_a to mean annual temperature and cumulative annual precipitation per study
252 site, in order to understand the possible climatic influence on the gas exchange fractionation.

253 Multiple linear models were fitted to explain BAI as a function of $iWUE$ and climate as
254 explanatory variables per study site for the period 1960-2012. Two sites (LLO_{ES} and CFI_{ES})
255 displayed an abrupt growth increase in the late 1960s that was related neither to climate nor to
256 $iWUE$; the most likely cause was due to intense logging activities (Natural Park
257 communications). Therefore, this decade was excluded from the analysis in these two sites and
258 the models were fitted for the period 1970-2012. Since the residuals of the BAI models were
259 not normally distributed, BAI was logarithmically transformed. Climate was represented by
260 seasonal mean temperatures and precipitation per study site (Table 2, Figure 1). Seasonal P/PET
261 values were excluded of the analyses since these were highly collinear to other explanatory
262 variables. A first-order autoregressive covariance structure (AR(1) model) was applied when
263 residuals of the models showed significant temporal autocorrelation. In these cases, the linear
264 models were fitted using generalized least squares (package nlme, Pinheiro et al., 2013). Model
265 selection and reduction of explanatory variables was done based on the Akaike's information
266 criteria (Akaike, 1974) corrected for small sample size (AICc). We considered as models with
267 substantial support those showing $\Delta AICc < 2$ (package MuMin; Bartoń, 2009). For a better
268 understanding of the effects of individual explanatory variables within the model, regression
269 coefficients were standardized by calculating the covariate effect. In order to do so and to
270 facilitate the comparison of the regression coefficients across models exhibiting different
271 distributions, the differences between the third and first quartiles for each explanatory variable
272 were calculated.

273 Finally, in order to provide an overview of the spatial patterns of BAI and $iWUE$, principal
274 component analyses (PCA) were performed for the common period 1960-2012. The climatic
275 influence on the spatial distribution patterns is usually related to inter-annual variability.

276 Therefore, these analyses were performed only taking into consideration the high-frequency
277 domain of the chronologies, which were obtained by high-pass filtering the series using a 20-
278 year spline (package *dplr*; Bunn, 2008). In order to assess the spatial patterns of similarities,
279 for each site, *BAI* and *iWUE* chronologies were correlated with the two first principal
280 components.

281 All the statistical analyses were performed using the different mentioned packages implemented in
282 the R statistical software (R Development Core Team 2008).

283

284 **Results**

285 *Climatic changes during the last decades*

286 Overall, temperatures (annual and seasonal means) increased at all study sites (1960-2012)
287 (Table 2), almost all of them significantly. Total annual precipitation decreased at all sites, but
288 only significantly at the western pine sites (LLO_{ES}, CUE_{FR} and BIO_{IT}), as well as at the oak
289 sites CFI_{ES} (Spain) and DOL_{SI} (Slovenia). Due to warming and decreasing cumulative annual
290 precipitation, the annual site aridity index (P/PET) displayed negative trends at all sites,
291 indicating drier conditions over the study period, all of them being significant except for the
292 two eastern sites in Bulgaria (VEL_{BG} and SUS_{BG}).

293 In general, summer was the season with the greatest temperature rise at all study sites ranging
294 between 0.03 and 0.05 °C year⁻¹, trends that always exceeded the corresponding ones in annual
295 mean temperature. Except for VEL_{BG}, summer precipitation generally decreased, however the
296 trends were only significant at LLO_{ES} (-1.31 mm year⁻¹) and DOL_{SI} (-1.83 mm year⁻¹). Summer
297 aridity significantly decreased at all western and central pine sites (LLO_{ES}, CUE_{FR}, BIO_{IT} and
298 MON_{IT}) as well as non-significantly at all oak sites indicating more severe drought conditions
299 over the time (except for DOL_{SI} being not arid in summer, but displaying significant changes).

300 *Long-term changes in growth and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -related series*

301 All chronologies showed a high degree of reliability (Table S1), as indicated by the Expressed
302 Population Signal (EPS) of the high-frequency chronologies (high-pass filtered data series, used
303 in the PCA analyses). All *BAI* and *iWUE* pine chronologies reached an EPS value above 0.85,
304 which is the well-accepted threshold in dendrochronology of chronology reliability (Wigley *et*
305 *al.*, 1984). Only *iWUE* chronologies from the oak sites with higher water availability (AST_{IT}
306 and DOL_{SI}) and SUS_{BG} displayed lower values of 0.72, 0.70 and 0.84, respectively.

307 Long-term changes in *BAI*, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, Δ , *Ci* and *iWUE* raw data were assessed to test for significant
308 changes in growth and gas exchange during the study period 1960-2012 (Table 3). *BAI* from
309 pine sites showed a general decreasing growth trend, all being significant except for VEL_{BG}
310 (Table 3). The easternmost pine site (VEL_{BG}) displayed the highest mean growth rate whereas
311 CUE_{FR} showed the lowest (Table 3). Conversely, *BAI* from central and eastern oak stands
312 (DOL_{SI} , SUS_{BG} and FOS_{RO}) significantly increased over time, whereas growth rates from the
313 most western or central stands, LLO_{ES} and AST_{IT} , significantly decreased or remained stable,
314 respectively. In the case of LLO_{ES} and CFI_{ES} , logging activities during the 1960s caused a
315 growth increase, as previously mentioned and, therefore, this decade was not included in the
316 analyses. Unlike the growth series, the ecophysiological proxies did not reflect the logging
317 effects of the 1960s at LLO_{ES} and CFI_{ES} .

318 The isotopic $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signature significantly decreased at all pine and oak sites, except for BIO_{IT} ,
319 the warmest and the wettest pine stand, and FOS_{BG} , the most eastern oak stand, where $\delta^{13}\text{C}$
320 values remained relatively constant over time (Table 3, Figure S1). Generally, pine sites
321 displayed relatively higher (less negative) ($-23.4 \text{ ‰} \pm 1.0$) values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ across study sites than
322 oak sites ($-24.2 \text{ ‰} \pm 1.4$). Significant negative trends were found for the Δ chronologies of the
323 western pine stands (LLO_{ES} , CUE_{FR} and BIO_{IT}) (Table 3, Figure 2), especially pronounced for
324 BIO_{IT} and with no significant trends for MON_{IT} and VEL_{BG} . In contrast, Δ chronologies of the

325 oak stands from AST_{IT}, DOL_{SI} and SUS_{BG} showed significant positive trends (but not
326 significant in SUS_{BG}), whereas the Δ values remained stable or decreased significantly in CFI_{ES}
327 and FOS_{RO}, respectively.

328 In general, the mean values for tree-ring $\delta^{13}C$ -derived C_i are slightly higher for oaks (190.8
329 ppmv \pm 25.6) than for pines (178.0 ppmv \pm 18.3), but all pine and oak stands showed significant
330 positive trends across the years, with MON_{IT} and AST_{IT} displaying the highest increased rates
331 for pine and oak, respectively. Equally, $iWUE$ registered significant positive trends at all sites,
332 regardless of the species. BIO_{IT} and FOS_{RO}, the two sites with no trend in the $\delta^{13}C$ signature,
333 showed the highest trends in $iWUE$ for pine and oak sites, respectively.

334 *Theoretical scenarios of C_i/C_a and their relationship with climate*

335 The results obtained comparing trends between the $\delta^{13}C$ -based C_i/C_a records and the three
336 theoretical gas-exchange scenarios of C_i/C_a evidenced clear differences between pine and oak
337 sites (Figure 3; Table S2). Time series of C_i/C_a ratios of most pine sites (4 out of 5) were closer
338 to the $C_i/C_a = \text{constant}$ scenario (scenario 2), except for BIO_{IT} (the warmest site) for which
339 C_i/C_a was closer to the $C_i = \text{constant}$ scenario (scenario 1). More diverse responses were found
340 among oak stands. At the oak sites with higher water availability AST_{IT} and DOL_{SI}, time series
341 of C_i/C_a ratios largely followed the $C_a - C_i = \text{constant}$ scenario (scenario 3). The two oak stands
342 at the east – west extremes, CFI_{ES} (Spain) and SUS_{BG} (Bulgaria), were close to $C_i/C_a =$
343 constant, whereas C_i/C_a from FOS_{RO} was the only time series close to $C_i = \text{constant}$ although
344 in recent years it approached the $C_i/C_a = \text{constant}$ scenario line.

345 The relationship between C_i/C_a and annual temperature was different between species (Figure
346 4). In the case of pine stands, C_i/C_a from the western stands (LLO_{ES}, CUE_{FR} and BIO_{IT}) was
347 significantly negatively related to annual temperature ($R^2 = 0.08, 0.13$ and 0.43 ; $p < 0.05$,
348 respectively); whereas C_i/C_a from central or eastern stands (MON_{IT} and VELG_{BG}), where

349 annual mean temperature was lower, did not show any significant relationship with annual
350 temperature. Regarding oak sites, the C_i/C_a from the stands displaying higher water availability
351 (AST_{IT} and DOL_{SI} , Table 2) were significantly positively related to temperatures. Conversely,
352 the moisture-limited oak sites from the east and the west were not sensitive to annual mean
353 temperature.

354 The relationship between the cumulative annual precipitation and C_i/C_a was significantly
355 positive at pine stands, except for MON_{IT} . Contrary to pines, none of the oak stands displayed
356 significant relationships of C_i/C_a with cumulative annual precipitation. Additionally, linear
357 regressions of oak C_i/C_a with seasonal precipitation did not display any clear pattern (Table
358 S3). Only the C_i/C_a from the most western stand (CFI_{ES}) was positively influenced by summer
359 precipitation and the C_i/C_a from DOL_{SI} and FOS_{RO} were negatively and positively related to
360 winter precipitation, respectively.

361 *BAI models based on $iWUE$ and climate*

362 *BAI* models for pine stands exhibited a larger percentage of variance explained than the models
363 for oak stands; 31.9-71.4% and 15.8-46.8%, respectively (Figure 5). In the case of pine stands,
364 the model from BIO_{IT} had the lowest explained variance whereas CUE_{FR} displayed the highest.
365 In the case of oak stands, the site with the highest water availability DOL_{SI} exhibited the lowest
366 explained variance, and CFI_{ES} (the warmest) the highest.

367 The positive increase of $iWUE$ over the 53-years study period (Table 3) was not linked to an
368 enhancement of *BAI* at most of the study sites (Figure 6, Table S4). In the selected models for
369 pine sites, *BAI* was negatively related to $iWUE$, except for MON_{IT} where $iWUE$ did not improve
370 the *BAI* model with climatic predictors only. *BAI* from LLO_{ES} and CUE_{FR} , the most western
371 stands, was more affected by changes in $iWUE$ than any other pine stands. The climatic
372 predictors included in the models varied among sites. Current winter and spring temperatures

373 positively affected *BAI* of LLO_{ES}, CUE_{FR} and VEL_{BG}. LLO_{ES} was the pine stand most sensitive
374 to spring temperatures. Previous and current autumn temperatures negatively influenced *BAI*
375 from MON_{IT}, whereas current summer temperature negatively affected *BAI* from CUE_{FR} and
376 MON_{IT}. In general, precipitation exerted a positive effect on *BAI*, but for different seasons, e.g.
377 previous autumn (CUE_{FR}, MON_{IT} and VEL_{BG}), spring (BIO_{IT} and VEL_{BG}) and summer (CUE_{FR}
378 and VEL_{BG}).

379 The change in *iWUE* linked to *BAI* at oak sites suggested a decreasing influence from west to
380 east. The most western stand (CFI_{ES}) contained the strongest negative relationship with changes
381 in *iWUE* whereas the most eastern stand (FOS_{RO}) was positively associated with *iWUE*.
382 However, *BAI* from SUS_{BG} seemed to be better explained by climatic predictors only since the
383 inclusion of *iWUE* did not improve the model.

384 Climatic predictors, generally precipitation, exerted a positive effect on *BAI* of the oak stands.
385 The site with the highest water availability DOL_{SI} was positively affected by previous summer,
386 current winter and current autumn temperatures. Spring and summer temperatures displayed a
387 positive effect on *BAI* from FOS_{RO} and SUS_{BG}, respectively. Regarding precipitation, previous
388 summer, winter preceding growth and current summer precipitation exerted a positive effect on
389 *BAI* from CFI_{ES}, AST_{IT} and SUS_{BG}, respectively. Previous autumn and current spring
390 precipitation showed positive partial regression coefficients with *BAI* from AST_{IT}, SUS_{BG} and
391 FOS_{RO}. *BAI* from FOS_{RO}, showed the largest sensitivity to lack of precipitation.

392 *Spatial patterns*

393 The results of the PCAs performed with the high-pass filtered chronologies of *BAI* and *iWUE*
394 for the period 1960-2012 revealed clear east-west geographical gradients for both PC1 and PC2
395 (Figure 7), overriding the potential site-specific and species-specific differences. In the case of
396 *BAI* chronologies, the common variance gathered by the first two PCs represented 45% of the

397 total variance. The first PC explained 27% and was significantly related to tree growth from the
398 western and central stands (LLO_{ES}, CFI_{ES}, CUE_{FR}, BIO_{IT}, AST_{IT}, MON_{IT} and DOL_{SI}). The
399 second PC explained 18% and was significantly correlated to *BAI* chronologies from eastern
400 stands (FOS_{RO}, SUS_{BG} and VEL_{BG}) and to a lesser degree to western and central stands CFI_{ES}
401 and MON_{IT}.

402 A nearly identical pattern was revealed for *iWUE*, that is, 51% of total variance was
403 explained by PC1 (29%) and PC2 (22%). *iWUE* chronologies from the western and central
404 Mediterranean (LLO_{ES}, CFI_{ES}, CUE_{FR}, BIO_{IT}, AST_{IT}, and MON_{IT}) were significantly correlated
405 with PC1. *iWUE* from the eastern sites (FOS_{RO}, SUS_{BG} and VEL_{BG}) and MON_{IT} and BIO_{IT}
406 were positively related to PC2, whereas the central and western DOL_{SI}, CUE_{FR}, LLO_{ES} and
407 CFI_{ES} were negatively correlated.

408

409 **Discussion**

410 *Intra- and inter-specific variability of isotope-based ecophysiological parameters*

411 The differences between pines and oaks in $\delta^{13}C$, Δ , C_i and *iWUE* at their southernmost
412 distribution limits in Europe likely result from their contrasting ecophysiology and functional
413 performance in the face of the ongoing climate change. Compared to sessile oak, Scots pine
414 showed lower Δ and, consequently, lower C_i , which translated into higher *iWUE* and a
415 decreasing growth trend during the studied period (Table 3). Scots pine is a species typically
416 performing a more conservative stomatal behavior than sessile oak under drought conditions
417 (Irvine *et al.*, 1998; Leo *et al.*, 2014; Salmon *et al.*, 2015; Lüpke *et al.*, 2016), which can lead
418 to zero gas exchange during prolonged dry spells (Poyatos *et al.*, 2013). Such a drought-
419 avoidance behavior reduces the risk of hydraulic failure but also compromises carbon uptake,
420 which forces trees to rely on carbon reserves (McDowell, 2011). An early stomata closure may

421 force Rubisco to reduce discrimination against ^{13}C , simultaneously leading to the reduction of
422 C_i in the intercellular space (Farquhar & Richards, 1984). The intra-specific variation among
423 pine sites clearly pointed to a covariation between Δ and precipitation. Pine stands with lower
424 annual precipitation (LLO_{ES} and VEL_{BG}) displayed higher (less negative) $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and a lower
425 discrimination against ^{13}C than the other three pine stands, due to their high sensitivity to water
426 stress. A similar gradient between water availability and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was found by Andreu-Hayles *et*
427 *al.* (2011) in pine populations across the Iberian Peninsula, and also under experimental
428 conditions where an increase in water availability was translated into lower (i.e. more negative)
429 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in Scots pine (Eilmann *et al.*, 2010; Timofeeva *et al.*, 2017). Appropriately, only western
430 stands (LLO_{ES}, CUE_{FR} and BIO_{IT}) experienced a significant decrease in precipitation as well as
431 a significant decreasing trend in ^{13}C discrimination, which reinforced the covariation between
432 pine Δ and precipitation (Table 2, Table 3).

433 In contrast to Scots pine, sessile oak showed higher discrimination against ^{13}C and higher C_i
434 concentrations which translated into lower $iWUE$ (Table 3). The drought-tolerance strategy of
435 sessile oak is linked to its capacity to maintain relatively high transpiration rates and stomatal
436 conductance during moderately dry conditions (Bréda *et al.*, 1993; Epron & Dreyer, 1993;
437 Aranda *et al.*, 2000), which allows this species to incorporate C_i for longer periods at the
438 expenses of high transpiration losses (lower $iWUE$). The oak sites with higher water availability
439 (AST_{IT} and DOL_{SI}) showed a significant increase in Δ throughout the study period. Although
440 both sites experienced a decrease in P/PET (Table 2), their water balance in the growing season
441 was still positive indicating comparably low or no drought stress.

442 Nevertheless, both studied species experienced an increase $iWUE$ as climate warmed, despite
443 their contrasting physiological strategies. This finding is in accordance with other studies on
444 different tree species at regional and global scales (Peñuelas *et al.*, 2011; Silva & Anand, 2013;
445 Saurer *et al.*, 2014; Frank *et al.*, 2015), but also at local scales (Waterhouse *et al.*, 2004; Andreu-

446 Hayles *et al.*, 2011; Rigling *et al.*, 2013; Granda *et al.*, 2014; Lévesque *et al.*, 2014). Moreover,
447 similar differences in C_i and $iWUE$ between pine and oak were also found in studies comparing
448 oaks and conifers (Frank *et al.*, 2015; Saurer *et al.*, 2014). However, both studies reported lower
449 $iWUE$ than our study, most probably due to a wider European geographical and climatic study
450 area. Since our study focused on populations located at the southern limit of the species'
451 distribution, lower stomatal conductance rates are expected, due to the drier conditions, and
452 therefore, higher $iWUE$.

453 *Physiological responses to Ca*

454 The response of the studied populations to increasing Ca is not uniform and depends on
455 additional factors such as species, site conditions, nutrients availability and climate (Saurer *et*
456 *al.*, 2014). However, our data showed consistent patterns over a large part of the Mediterranean
457 region. Scots pine populations were able to track increases of Ca during the last 60 years
458 keeping C_i/Ca constant, except for BIO_{IT} (the warmest site) that displayed a constant C_i over
459 the studied period (Figure 3, Table S2). The $C_i/Ca = \text{constant}$ behavior reflects a proportional
460 regulation of A and g_s affecting C_i . However, the significant negative trend of C_i/Ca at BIO_{IT}
461 following the $C_i = \text{constant}$ scenario implied a low / no sensitivity to increasing levels of Ca ,
462 indicating that other factors, such as temperature and drought, reinforced the stomatal closure.
463 Although the $C_i/Ca = \text{constant}$ scenario is the most common response of conifers in Eurasia
464 (Saurer *et al.*, 2004), as well as of pine populations in the Iberian Peninsula (Andreu-Hayles *et*
465 *al.*, 2011), no agreement exists on whether $C_i = \text{constant}$ is the most common scenario for
466 declining (Voltas *et al.*, 2013) or non-declining Scots pine trees (Hereş *et al.*, 2014).

467 Our results also revealed that C_i/Ca of western and central pine stands (LLO_{ES}, CUE_{FR} and
468 BIO_{IT}) was significantly restricted by high temperatures, especially at the warmest site (BIO_{IT}).
469 Precipitation also exerted a significant positive effect on C_i/Ca , especially in stands with lower
470 annual precipitation (LLO_{ES} and VEL_{BG}). Therefore, high temperatures and reduced

471 precipitation seem to be the main limitations for carbon uptake of trees at BIO_{IT}, most likely
472 due to the strict stomatal control described for Scots pine, resulting in a decoupling of
473 intercellular concentrations from rising C_a ($C_i = \text{constant}$). The other western pine stands
474 (LLO_{ES} and CUE_{FR}) followed the $C_i/C_a = \text{constant}$ scenario more closely but both sites
475 displayed significant negative C_i/C_a trends over time ($p < 0.05$) which future higher
476 temperatures might intensify similarly to BIO_{IT}.

477 We found a higher variability in C_i responses to rising C_a trends across the sessile oak sites.
478 C_i/C_a followed the $C_i = \text{constant}$ scenario at the driest site (FOS_{RO}) and at the less dry sites gas
479 exchange was regulated towards optimizing C_i/C_a (constant- C_i/C_a scenario, CFI_{ES} and
480 SUS_{BG}). In contrast, C_i/C_a at sites with higher water availability (AST_{IT} and DOL_{SI}) followed
481 the $C_a-C_i = \text{constant}$ scenario, which implies a very weak stomatal response to C_a and
482 environmental conditions, and a lower increase in $iWUE$ (Saurer *et al.*, 2004). Unlike the pine
483 populations, C_i/C_a of oaks was unrelated to annual precipitation, regardless of the differences
484 in total precipitation among oak populations. However, C_i/C_a trends at the two sites with higher
485 water availability (AST_{IT} and DOL_{SI}) were significantly positively influenced by temperatures,
486 suggesting that warming stimulates higher photosynthetic rates. In contrast to Scots pine,
487 studies analyzing the regulation of gas exchange of sessile oak at its southernmost distribution
488 edge are lacking. Although European-scale studies suggested that $C_i/C_a = \text{constant}$ and C_a-C_i
489 $= \text{constant}$ scenarios are the most common carbon exchange scenarios for *Quercus* spp. (Saurer
490 *et al.*, 2014; Frank *et al.*, 2015), these are based on stands located far from their southern
491 distribution limit. Our study indicates a high site-to-site variability among oak sites which is
492 valuable to understand the carbon exchange dynamics of this species in the Mediterranean
493 region.

494 *Tree growth relationships to iWUE and climate*

495 Basal area increment was negatively related to *iWUE* at most of our studies sites, and this
496 relationship was even stronger for pine stands (Figure 6). Thus, the increase of *iWUE* since
497 1960 generally has not been translated into enhanced growth. A negative relationship between
498 *BAI* and *iWUE* is most commonly reported in global studies (Peñuelas *et al.*, 2011; Silva &
499 Anand, 2013 and references therein), and especially for isohydric species (Granda *et al.*, 2014;
500 Lévesque *et al.*, 2014; Olano *et al.*, 2014) and particularly for Scots pine stands (Hereş *et al.*,
501 2014; but see Martínez-Vilalta *et al.*, 2008). This fact mirrors an increasingly harsh climate in
502 the recent decades, particularly for pines, suggesting a prevailing reduction in stomatal
503 conductance rather than an increase in photosynthetic rates (Maseyk *et al.*, 2011; Voltas *et al.*,
504 2013). The drought-avoidance strategy of Scots pine has resulted in reduced transpiration rates
505 over time, but this may have also been the main growth limitation. The beneficial effect of
506 increased *iWUE* in pines is most likely the protection against cell turgor loss and failure of the
507 hydraulic system (Körner, 2015). However, higher *iWUE* rates are also associated with the cost
508 of reduced CO₂ uptake, and consequently negative growth trends, considering *BAI* as a
509 surrogate of carbon assimilation. Moreover, reduced photosynthesis may also lead to a
510 progressive depletion of stored carbohydrates because freshly produced assimilates cannot
511 cover all carbon needs of the trees, that is, metabolism, defense and growth (Rigling *et al.*,
512 2013).

513 In our models for Scots pine, the growth variability not attributable to changes in *iWUE* was
514 mainly related to climatic conditions during the growing season. Spring temperatures, which
515 significantly increased at all locations, exerted a positive effect on *BAI*, most likely due to an
516 earlier onset of growth (Menzel & Fabian, 1999; Gordo & Sanz, 2010; Kraus *et al.*, 2016). In
517 contrast, summer temperatures positively influenced growth at the eastern stand VEL_{BG}
518 whereas summer and autumn temperatures negatively affected *BAI* at the western and central
519 pine stands. The negative influence of autumn temperature could be associated with the
520 extension of the stressful conditions (summer), particularly when coupled with reduced

521 precipitation (Andreu *et al.*, 2007) Precipitation displayed fewer significant regression
522 coefficients in *BAI* models than temperature, but its influence was always positive as expected
523 in drought-prone areas (Ferrio *et al.*, 2003; Andreu *et al.*, 2007; Benito Garzón *et al.*, 2011;
524 Sánchez-Salguero *et al.*, 2016).

525 Contrasting relationships between growth and *iWUE* were found among the oak stands.
526 Interestingly, these relationships showed a clear east-west pattern with negative correlations in
527 the three western and central stands (CFI_{ES}, AST_{IT} and DOL_{SI}), but not as strong as in the case
528 of pines, and positive correlations in the most eastern stand. Such a spatial pattern points to a
529 diverging *iWUE*-growth relationship in oak. Interestingly, large differences in the total annual
530 precipitation were observed in the three western and central stands (CFI_{ES}, AST_{IT} and DOL_{SI})
531 that covariates with effects that *iWUE* has on *BAI*.

532 The two eastern oak stands (SUS_{BG} and FOS_{RO}) are under the influence of a continental climate
533 with rather mild however dry climatic conditions during summer. With almost constant or even
534 increasing autumn precipitation, both stands displayed significant increasing *BAI* trends. The
535 *Ci* = constant scenario displayed by FOS_{RO} might have an important role to avoid possible water
536 loss due to transpiration and, certainly, sessile oaks from FOS_{RO} may have benefited from CO₂-
537 induced growth enhancement. However, this positive correlation between *iWUE* and *BAI* is not
538 commonly reported except for some studies on conifers, that is, *Fitzroya cupressoides* in the
539 Andes (Urrutia-Jalabert *et al.*, 2015), *Juniperus thurifera* in the Iberian Peninsula (Granda *et*
540 *al.*, 2014), and *Abies cephalonica* in Greece (Koutavas, 2013), and further research is needed
541 to support these conclusions.

542 In oak, the variability of growth not related to *iWUE* was mainly associated with precipitation,
543 which always exerted a positive effect on *BAI*. The dominance of precipitation influence over
544 other climatic drivers seems to be common for oak populations, even under mesic conditions
545 (González-González *et al.*, 2013; Delpierre *et al.*, 2016; Martínez-Sancho *et al.*, 2017). In

546 addition, temperature exerted little but positive effects on *BAI*, particularly in central and
547 eastern populations pointing to non-drought induced growth limitations. This positive
548 temperature effect in combination with the increase in *iWUE* could have contributed to the
549 positive *BAI* trends of the central and eastern sites in comparison to the most western stands.

550 *Spatial patterns*

551 In addition to the above mentioned physiological differences between the two tree species, the
552 intra-annual variability of the growth and *iWUE* chronologies clearly displayed an east-west
553 geographical pattern masking possible species-specific differences. These results agree with
554 those reported by Seim *et al.* (2014) who found a distinct east-west dipole in tree growth of
555 pine species at the Mediterranean Basin. Chen *et al.* (2015) and Dorado-Liñán *et al.* (2017)
556 reported a similar spatial pattern across the Mediterranean Basin in growth of broadleaf
557 deciduous tree species and related such a pattern to summer climatic conditions. More recently,
558 a similar gradient was found for wood anatomy of oak stands (Martínez-Sancho *et al.*, 2017)
559 and our results describe this geographical polarity for the first time also for ecophysiological
560 parameters. This geographical pattern has been recently linked to variations in the Summer
561 North Atlantic Oscillation (SNAO) and the differential influence that this atmospheric
562 circulation pattern exerts on summer precipitation and temperature across the Mediterranean
563 Basin (Dorado-Liñán *et al.*, 2017). Although further detailed analyses are needed, the same
564 geographical dipole found in growth, anatomical and isotope series may indicate a whole-tree
565 response to the same climatic forcing.

566 *Future implications*

567 Overall, the general increase in *iWUE* at our study sites has translated into different growth
568 patterns which could be linked to the ecophysiology of the two contrasting species. The growth
569 decline observed in all Scots pine stands shows that, despite increased *iWUE* the reduced

570 stomatal conductance limits the photosynthetic activity and thus the accumulation of carbon
571 reserves used for growth, maintenance and potentially defences (Cailleret *et al.*, 2017). This
572 may influence the species' acclimation potential to future short- and long-term unfavourable
573 conditions. In contrast, the growth response of sessile oak to changes in *iWUE* was found to be
574 much more variable across sites. While eastern stands could still benefit growth-wise from the
575 increase in *iWUE*, growth of the most western stands was already restricted under current
576 climate change, similarly to pine growth, mostly by precipitation declines which could not be
577 compensated even with a more relaxed stomatal behaviour of this species. In the case of sessile
578 oak, our results are in line with those studies suggesting that tissue formation is inhibited by
579 drought long before carbon supply falls short because of drought induced limitations of gas
580 exchange (Delpierre *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, our results strongly suggest that the complex
581 regionally and species-specific varying relationships between *iWUE*, growth and seasonal
582 climate factors should be studied in full detail in order to assess future impacts of climate change
583 on forests.

584

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853 **Tables**

854 **Table 1.** Geographical and structural characteristics of the study sites. Standard deviations are
 855 shown in parentheses. LAT, latitude; LON, longitude; DBH, diameter at breast height; TRW,
 856 tree-ring width; SLA, specific leaf area.

SITE				LAT	LON	ALTITUDE	DBH	HEIGHT	TRW	SLA
NAME	CODE	COUNTRY	SPECIES	(°N)	(°E)	(m a.s.l.)	(cm)	(m)	SPAN	(cm ² /g)
Sant Llorenç del Munt	LLO _{ES}	Spain	<i>P. sylvestris</i>	41.72	2.00	500	30.1 (4.2)	10.9 (0.9)	1908-2013	NA
Cuébris	CUE _{FR}	France	<i>P. sylvestris</i>	43.89	7.06	720	38.1 (7.2)	10.0 (1.8)	1927-2013	NA
Baiardo	BIO _{IT}	Italy	<i>P. sylvestris</i>	43.92	7.76	870	40.6 (11.9)	13.4 (2.2)	1874-2013	10.7
Monte Sole	MON _{IT}	Italy	<i>P. sylvestris</i>	44.29	11.18	560	35.2 (8.4)	12.2 (1.7)	1941-2013	17.6
Velingrad	VEL _{BG}	Bulgaria	<i>P. sylvestris</i>	42.03	23.96	815	49.6 (7.6)	20.7 (23.1)	1898-2012	21.2
Can Figueroles	CFI _{ES}	Spain	<i>Q. petraea</i>	41.81	2.38	1046	35.8 (5.0)	11.9 (1.5)	1926-2012	76.8
RocchetaTanaro	AST _{IT}	Italy	<i>Q. petraea</i>	44.86	8.32	187	52.4 (10.0)	18.2 (2.5)	1900-2012	113.8
Dolenja	DOL _{SI}	Slovenia	<i>Q. petraea</i>	45.75	14.03	644	37.2 (4.8)	18.7 (2.5)	1886-2012	82.9
Sushitsa	SUS _{BG}	Bulgaria	<i>Q. petraea</i>	41.82	23.08	844	36.0 (4.2)	16.8 (1.9)	1899-2012	90.9
Focsani	FOS _{RO}	Romania	<i>Q. petraea</i>	45.81	27.02	382	45.0 (8.9)	18.4 (1.6)	1864-2012	75.5

857

858 **Table 2.** Annual and seasonal temperature, precipitation and aridity (P/PET) means and their
859 temporal trends for all study sites. The data were obtained from the CRU TS3.23 dataset. The
860 trend is the slope of a linear regression for the period 1960-2012 of the respective annual means
861 against year; the significance of the trends is denoted by stars *. p -value < 0.05; **, p -value <
862 0.01.

Scots pine		LLO _{ES}		CUE _{FR}		BIO _{IT}		MON _{IT}		VEL _{BG}	
		Mean ± SD	Trend	Mean ± SD	Trend						
Temperature (°C)	Winter	6.5 ± 0.9	0.01	6.6 ± 0.8	0.02**	7.2 ± 0.8	0.02*	1.9 ± 1.0	0.01	-2.7 ± 1.1	0.01
	Spring	11.1 ± 0.8	0.02**	11.5 ± 0.8	0.03**	12.3 ± 0.8	0.03**	9.2 ± 0.8	0.02**	6.7 ± 1.0	0.02*
	Summer	20.4 ± 1.0	0.03**	20.3 ± 1.0	0.05**	21.1 ± 0.9	0.05**	19.2 ± 0.9	0.04**	16.8 ± 1.1	0.04**
	Autumm	14.1 ± 0.8	0.02**	14.2 ± 0.8	0.03**	15.0 ± 0.8	0.03**	11.4 ± 0.8	0.02**	8.1 ± 0.9	0.01
	Annual	13.0 ± 0.6	0.02**	13.2 ± 0.6	0.03**	13.9 ± 0.6	0.03**	10.4 ± 0.5	0.03**	7.2 ± 0.6	0.02**
Precipitation (mm)	Winter	121.3 ± 67.7	-0.92	230.2 ± 105.5	-1.99*	230.3 ± 100.2	-1.97*	183.9 ± 65.1	-1.07	157.1 ± 55.5	-0.11
	Spring	184.6 ± 69.5	-0.35	205.2 ± 86.8	-0.81	206.1 ± 81.2	-0.79	192.8 ± 59.4	-1.17*	204.6 ± 50.3	-0.47
	Summer	152.2 ± 69.5	-1.31*	128.5 ± 78.0	-1.22	119.8 ± 68.1	-1.04	173.6 ± 61.4	-0.81	210.3 ± 76.9	0.01
	Autumm	203.2 ± 76.0	-0.97	299.2 ± 141.1	-1.64	312.1 ± 133.0	-1.23	273.6 ± 97.5	0.21	158.2 ± 60.7	0.34
	Annual	660.4 ± 145.0	-3.60**	860.5 ± 219.5	-5.51**	865.7 ± 197.2	-4.85**	821.0 ± 172.3	-2.67	730.9 ± 132.5	-0.25
P/PET	Winter	1.1 ± 0.6	-0.010	1.9 ± 0.9	-0.018*	2.0 ± 0.9	-0.017*	3.5 ± 1.3	-0.017*	2.0 ± 0.7	0.001
	Spring	0.8 ± 0.3	-0.002	0.9 ± 0.4	-0.007	0.9 ± 0.4	-0.007*	1.1 ± 0.4	-0.010**	1.0 ± 0.3	-0.004
	Summer	0.4 ± 0.2	-0.004*	0.3 ± 0.2	-0.004*	0.3 ± 0.2	-0.004*	0.5 ± 0.2	-0.004*	0.6 ± 0.2	-0.001
	Autumm	1.2 ± 0.5	-0.009*	1.8 ± 0.9	-0.015	1.9 ± 0.9	-0.012	2.7 ± 1.2	0.000	1.2 ± 0.5	-0.001
	Annual	0.7 ± 0.2	-0.005**	0.9 ± 0.3	-0.008**	0.9 ± 0.2	-0.007**	1.1 ± 0.3	-0.05*	0.9 ± 0.2	-0.002
Sessile oak		CFI _{ES}		AST _{IT}		DOL _{SI}		SUS _{BG}		FOS _{RO}	
		Mean ± SD	Trend	Mean ± SD	Trend						
Temperature (°C)	Winter	7.2 ± 0.9	0.01	3.6 ± 0.9	0.02**	-0.5 ± 1.2	0.03*	-1.6 ± 1.1	0.01	-1.1 ± 1.6	0.02
	Spring	11.5 ± 0.8	0.02**	12.1 ± 1.0	0.04**	7.6 ± 1.0	0.03**	7.4 ± 1.0	0.02*	10.6 ± 1.2	0.03**
	Summer	20.7 ± 1.0	0.03**	21.2 ± 1.0	0.05**	16.6 ± 1.0	0.04**	17.5 ± 1.1	0.04**	21.0 ± 1.0	0.04**
	Autumm	14.6 ± 0.8	0.02**	13.0 ± 0.8	0.02**	9.1 ± 0.9	0.02**	9.0 ± 0.9	0.01	11.1 ± 1.0	0.00
	Annual	13.5 ± 0.6	0.02**	12.5 ± 0.7	0.03**	8.2 ± 0.7	0.03**	8.1 ± 0.6	0.02**	10.4 ± 0.7	0.02**
Precipitation (mm)	Winter	134.3 ± 78.9	-0.66	213.7 ± 102.1	-1.13	344.4 ± 140.7	-1.63	149.6 ± 54.3	-0.29	85.5 ± 31.7	-0.049
	Spring	189.2 ± 82.0	-0.73	275.1 ± 94.4	-0.58	378.6 ± 99.0	-1.02	186.7 ± 47.5	-0.47	132.2 ± 46.7	-0.251
	Summer	158.9 ± 68.8	-0.83	209.9 ± 79.6	-0.57	399.6 ± 93.6	-1.83*	178.8 ± 71.8	-0.25	189.3 ± 57.2	-0.421
	Autumm	212.5 ± 85.2	-1.53*	347.1 ± 147.2	-0.31	529.1 ± 184.1	-0.47	150.1 ± 57.7	0.24	115.8 ± 48.7	0.282
	Annual	694.0 ± 175.3	-3.84*	1042.5 ± 215.0	-2.32	1674.9 ± 233.5	-4.58*	665.4 ± 119.0	-0.82	523.8 ± 90.2	-0.325
P/PET	Winter	1.2 ± 0.7	-0.007	4.3 ± 2.1	-0.014	8.1 ± 3.9	-0.045	1.9 ± 0.7	-0.001	2.7 ± 2.0	-0.012
	Spring	0.8 ± 0.4	-0.004	1.3 ± 0.5	-0.009	2.6 ± 0.9	-0.012	0.9 ± 0.2	-0.004	0.6 ± 0.3	-0.004
	Summer	0.4 ± 0.2	-0.003	0.6 ± 0.3	-0.003	1.4 ± 0.4	-0.008*	0.5 ± 0.2	-0.001	0.5 ± 0.2	-0.002
	Autumm	1.2 ± 0.6	-0.012*	3.3 ± 1.8	-0.008	6.2 ± 3.1	-0.035	1.1 ± 0.4	-0.001	1.1 ± 0.6	-0.004
	Annual	0.7 ± 0.2	-0.005**	1.3 ± 0.3	-0.006*	2.5 ± 0.5	-0.011**	0.8 ± 0.2	-0.002	0.6 ± 0.1	-0.002*

863 **Table 3.** Characteristics of tree growth and carbon isotope variables during the study period
864 (1960-2012). *BAI*, basal area increment; Δ , ^{13}C discrimination; *Ci*, leaf intercellular CO_2
865 concentration; *iWUE*, intrinsic water-use efficiency. Note: the rates of change per year are
866 calculated as the slopes of the linear regressions. For *BAI* at LLO_{ES} and CFI_{ES} means and rates
867 are calculated for the period 1970-2012, as explained in the methods. *, *p*-value < 0.05; **, *p*-
868 value < 0.01.

Scots pine	LLO_{ES}		CUE_{FR}		BIO_{IT}		MON_{IT}		VEL_{BG}	
	Mean \pm SD	Rate	Mean \pm SD	Rate	Mean \pm SD	Rate	Mean \pm SD	Rate	Mean \pm SD	Rate
<i>BAI</i> ($\text{mm}^2 \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$)	723.4 \pm 187.5	-6.89**	1127.0 \pm 319.2	-17.09**	923.5 \pm 254.3	-9.16**	934.9 \pm 250.8	-9.06**	1343.3 \pm 372.0	-1.98
$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)	-23.0 \pm 0.5	-0.02**	-23.6 \pm 0.5	-0.02**	-24.1 \pm 0.4	0.00	-23.7 \pm 0.5	-0.03**	-22.5 \pm 0.7	-0.03**
Δ (‰)	15.7 \pm 0.4	-0.01**	16.4 \pm 0.4	-0.01*	16.9 \pm 0.6	-0.03**	16.5 \pm 0.3	0.00	15.3 \pm 0.6	0.00
<i>Ci</i> (ppmv)	172.0 \pm 11.1	0.58**	181.6 \pm 11.4	0.67**	188.8 \pm 7.8	0.31**	183.0 \pm 13.2	0.77**	164.8 \pm 14.3	0.67**
<i>iWUE</i> ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	110.8 \pm 9.5	0.57**	104.9 \pm 8.7	0.51**	100.4 \pm 11.9	0.74**	104.0 \pm 7.7	0.45**	115.4 \pm 9.5	0.51**
Sessile oak	CFI_{ES}		AST_{IT}		DOL_{SI}		SUS_{BG}		FOS_{RO}	
	Mean \pm SD	Rate	Mean \pm SD	Rate	Mean \pm SD	Rate	Mean \pm SD	Rate	Mean \pm SD	Rate
<i>BAI</i> ($\text{mm}^2 \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$)	1581.9 \pm 372.1	-10.77*	3284.0 \pm 617.2	4.41	1589.9 \pm 317.9	14.04**	1262.9 \pm 234.2	5.33**	1837.0 \pm 668.2	25.41**
$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)	-24.7 \pm 0.7	-0.03**	-23.2 \pm 1.0	-0.06**	-24.5 \pm 0.9	-0.05**	-24.7 \pm 0.7	-0.04**	-23.6 \pm 0.8	0.00
Δ (‰)	17.5 \pm 0.6	0.00	16.0 \pm 0.7	0.03**	17.3 \pm 0.6	0.02**	17.5 \pm 0.5	0.01	16.4 \pm 0.9	-0.03**
<i>Ci</i> (ppmv)	198.9 \pm 16.2	0.85**	176.6 \pm 20.6	1.22**	196.9 \pm 19.6	1.14**	199.3 \pm 16.9	0.97**	182.3 \pm 15.2	0.42**
<i>iWUE</i> ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	94.1 \pm 8.1	0.40**	108.0 \pm 5.5	0.17**	95.3 \pm 5.8	0.22**	93.8 \pm 6.6	0.33**	104.4 \pm 12.7	0.67**

869

870

871 **Figures**

872 **Figure 1.** Location and climate of the ten study sites at the southern edge of the distribution
873 area of Scots pine and sessile oak. Upper left panel refers to Scots pine and upper right panel to
874 sessile oak. Maps modified from those available at www.euforgen.org. Bottom panels show the
875 climatograms of the ten study sites using CRU TS 3.23 dataset (for details of the study sites see
876 Table 1).

877

878

879 **Figure 2.** Annually resolved tree-ring $\Delta^{13}C$ series per study site for the period 1960-2012. Site
880 abbreviations as in Table 1; see also Fig. 1 for site locations. Colored lines correspond to the
881 different trees and black lines represent the trend of the mean chronology per site (see details
882 of the trends in Table 3).

883

884

885 **Figure 3.** Observed C_i/C_a values (grey circles), trend of observed data (grey line) against trends
 886 of the three theoretical scenarios for all the study sites. Const, constant.

— $C_i = \text{const}$ — $C_i / Ca = \text{const}$ — $Ca - C_i = \text{const}$

887

888 **Figure 4.** Linear regressions of C_i/Ca against annual mean temperature and cumulative annual
 889 precipitation for all study sites. Left and right panels refer to annual temperature total annual
 890 precipitation, respectively. Values at the bottom indicate R^2 and their significance is coded with
 891 *, p -value < 0.05; **, p -value < 0.01; ***, p -value < 0.001.

892

893 **Figure 5.** Observed (red lines) and predicted (black line) basal area increments in all the study
 894 sites. The predictions were based on models simulations including *iWUE* and seasonal
 895 temperatures and precipitations. Grey area indicates the 95% confidence intervals of the model.

896

897 **Figure 6.** Effect of *iWUE* and seasonal temperatures and precipitations on *BAI* per study site.
 898 Blue points and bars refer to positive effects whereas red ones refer to negative. Note:
 899 Regression coefficients from the best-supported linear models were standardized by calculating
 900 the difference between the third and first quartiles for each explanatory variable in order to
 901 facilitate the comparison across models. T, temperature; P, precipitation; p, previous year
 902 values.

903

904 **Figure 7.** Pearson correlation coefficients between *BAI* and *iWUE* site chronologies and the
 905 first and second principal components. Significance at 0.05 level. *BAI*, basal area increment;
 906 *iWUE*, intrinsic water-use efficiency.

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909

910 **Supporting information**

911 Figure S1. Individual raw annually resolved tree-ring $\delta^{13}C$ series per study site for the common
912 period 1960-2012.

913 Table S1. Characteristics of high-pass filtered basal area increment and water-use efficiency
914 chronologies.

915 Table S2. The similarities of the Ci/Ca trends obtained from the $\delta^{13}C$ -values and the three
916 theoretical scenarios per study site.

917 Table S3. Linear regressions of Ci/Ca against seasonal precipitation sums for the oak sites. *,
918 p -value < 0.05; **, p -value < 0.01; ***, p -value < 0.001.

919 Table S4. Regression coefficients of the best-supported linear models per study site.

920